

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MAZZA****FIRST NAME: ANTHONY****PROGRAM CODE: DCTD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MS Word version 14.4.0 on MAC 10.13.6, 2015)

PERIOD ONE RESPONSE PAPER

1) INTRODUCTION

Academic publications “attempt to persuade” and involve the communication of a concept based on evidence. Academic publications begin with a thesis, and construct an informed argument based on research (EUCLID 2019, 7). Euclid University has developed a course methodology for writing standards, relevant for the various academic levels. For PhD-level programs, the University has mandated ACA-401: International Academic and Professional Paper Writing. This response paper will discuss five key notions presented in the “essential concepts of academic writing” tutorial and will rely primarily on the coursepack provided for this course.

Euclid University draws students from six continents. Though the University instructs in English, differences in grammar, usage, construction, context and vocabulary have compelled the institution to establish writing criteria to facilitate communication (EUCLID 2019, 11). The University has adopted the “Turabian style” as a guide for writing and formatting academic publications (EUCLID 2019, 29). Published by the University of Chicago Press, the Turabian style is named for its author (Kate Turabian) and is often referred to as the “Chicago style” of writing (EUCLID 2019, 49). As such, the Turabian style of writing has prescribed standards that have been codified in the coursepack, along with general suggestions for academic publications. Personally, the five most interesting concepts discussed in the coursepack are: avoiding plagiarism; literature review guidelines; American v. British English; Latin phrases and usage; and, lexicalization. Each of these concepts will be explored herein.

2) AVOIDING PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is the representation, duplication or usage of concepts or expressions belonging to another without ascribing credit (EUCLID 2019, 5). The implication is that the author is dishonestly presenting information as proprietary. Euclid University considers plagiarism to be academically dishonest and unethical and has provided students with strategies to avoid misrepresenting the work of others (EUCLID 2019, 5-12). The coursepack outlines quotation usage, citation practices and footnoting procedures. Among the more helpful suggestions is the encouragement to use “signal phrases” to alert the reader of the incorporation of a third-party concept. According to Dr. Cleenewerck and Dr. Gulma, “using signal phrases introduces a quotation or paraphrase”^[1] and is an effective tactic to avoid plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 10).

3) LITERATURE REVIEW GUIDELINES

At the core of every academic publication is the research element that supports the thesis. A literature review is a summation of research that presents substantive findings, theoretical conjecture and methodological contributions to a particular topic (University of North Carolina, 2020). As the basis for research in virtually all academic fields, organizing Literature Reviews follows a series of conventions. The coursepack provides several strategies for arranging third party information to comport with convention (EUCLID 2019, 17-23).

4) AMERICAN V. BRITISH ENGLISH

The minor divergence in the forms of English usage in the United States v. other predominantly English-language nations has produced variation in spelling and usage. Emanating from “differing national histories and cultural development” (EUCLID 2019, 27). But the few variations in vocabulary provide the opportunity for embarrassing or humorous miscommunication. This topic calls to mind the famous quote attributed to Oscar Wilde in his 1887 short story *The Canterville Ghost*: Britons have “everything in common with Americans except language.” The coursepack provides a succinct summation of the common differences to illustrate their proper usage (EUCLID 2019, 28-31).

5) LATIN PHRASES AND USAGE

Particularly helpful is the compendium of Latin phrases organized at the end of the coursepack (EUCLID 2019, 56-61). Compiled as a simple reference tool, the Latin phrases identified enjoy common usage in academic publications and can be utilized by Euclid University students *ad libitum*.

6) LEXICALIZATION

By far the most interesting information communicated in period one was the introduction of lexicalization. Lexicalization is the process of “vocabulary addition” by adding new words to a language that have gained widespread usage. The coursepack has identified several current examples (EUCLID 2019, 31-34). Profound and profane, the examples provided included regional variations, “politically correct” speech and obscenities- both implicit and implied.

7) CONCLUSION

The coursepack provides the necessary reference material to begin the appreciation for the expectations for academic writing for the Ph.D. program at Euclid University. I found the material to be comprehensive, informative and understandable. I am certain that I will be utilizing the coursepack throughout this academic journal, which I am both humbled and excited to begin.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA- 401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University Press.

University of North Carolina. 2020. *Literature Reviews*. The Writing Center. Chapel Hill. <https://writingcenter.unc.edu/tips-and-tools/literature-reviews/> (accessed July 2, 2020).

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.